

**SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF MODERNIZATION OF
SPIRITUAL-EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY.**

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Annotation: The system of spiritual and educational work is the interrelated socio-political, legal, socio-economic, ideological-ideological, educational system of state and non-state organizations under the leadership of the Republican Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment, consists of a complex of cultural and educational events.

Keywords: Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees and decisions, decisions, orders, statements, regulatory legal documents.

The system of spiritual and educational work includes the following structures:

preschool education aimed at forming and developing social and spiritual values, the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, general secondary educational schools, secondary special, vocational education and higher educational institutions;

state and non-state organizations, local authorities and management bodies, enterprises, organizations and institutions, law enforcement agencies, veterans' councils, structures of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan and other organizations that carry out spiritual and educational work in the country. Spiritual and educational work is carried out on a regular, systematic and scientific basis, and state and non-state organizations, all subjects of this activity are responsible for its effectiveness.

The main subjects of spiritual and educational work are state and local authorities; state and non-state non-profit organizations, civil society institutions;

families; Youth Union of Uzbekistan; preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special education, vocational education and higher education institutions; cultural and sports institutions (theatre, museum, historical monuments, cinema, library, parks, etc.); mass media, literature, art institutions; organizes children's health camps and others.

The objects of spiritual and educational work are all citizens and youth of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of nationality, language, gender, social affiliation, in particular: students of pre-school educational institutions; students of general secondary educational institutions, secondary special, vocational educational institutions and students of higher educational institutions; unorganized youth; citizens working in state and private enterprises; are luminaries, labor veterans.

Preventive programs and socio-pedagogical projects implemented in our country show that there is a favorable scientific ground for the integration of the goals and tasks of the spiritual and educational work carried out in our country with world experience. In this regard, the opinions of foreign researchers A. Goldstein, U. Engels, C. Kochlar-Bryant, R. Lacey, J. Leonard and others about pedagogical measures conducted with unorganized youth and organizing mobile pedagogical work with youth study of the materials of international symposia dedicated to this will serve the emergence of a number of new approaches in this regard.

It is noticeable that social and educational activities are carried out in connection with leisure in Western countries. The deep immersion of people in the virtual world and their separation from the real world is becoming a universal problem. An example is the book called "99 francs" by the French thinker Frederic Begbender. He wrote in his bestseller: "True hedonism means enjoying the life around us. But people are doing the opposite: they are glued to television, phones, movies, internet, video game fashion magazines. They do not participate in existing life, they are afraid to even breathe "here and now" and prefer to live in another dimension. A

person watching TV, answering interactive questions, talking on a mobile phone or playing on his "Playstation" is not living. He is not here. "He has passed to another world . "

Based on the different names of recreation and meaningful spending of free time in Western countries, they can be called "leisure-recreational activity" or "cultural-recreational activity" in general. In both approaches, the complex nature of the activity, social orientation is visible. "Leisure-recreational activity" serves to restore the physical and mental health of a person. "Cultural-recreational activity" is intended not only to provide recreation, but also to increase the cultural (therefore, spiritual) level of people.

In the West, a concept has been created that takes into account the theoretical and practical issues of recreation, in which recreation is defined as the freedom of a person from his civil, professional and family obligations. It is understood that he is engaged in social and cultural creativity, increasing his knowledge. As you can see, the concept of leisure in Western countries shows that it has physiological, psychological, educational, aesthetic, communicative, compensatory and creative functions. In the traditional interpretation, three main functions are used separately. These are recreation, leisure and physical and spiritual development. The harmony of the function of spiritual development with the functions of the system of spiritual and educational work of Uzbekistan shows how useful it is to study the achievements in this regard.

As noted in the table, the American model of **“entertainment+enlightenment”** is dominated by the function of recreation. In the European model, more attention is paid to the spiritual development of the individual. In Switzerland, Germany and France, "socio-cultural animation" activities take the lead, in which the social-pedagogical direction of leisure activities takes priority. Currently, the elements of this direction can be seen in the experience of spiritual and educational work of our country. For example, during Nowruz,

Independence Day and other spiritual and educational events, together with lectures on socio-political, legal, cultural topics, theater actors, famous singers, pop singers, and wordsmiths will perform together. what they are doing is proof of that. This is a positive example of the "Hordiq+enlightenment" formula, which prevents events from becoming official and politicized. Based on the above, it is necessary to constantly pay attention to the correct assessment of the balance of leisure and enlightenment in spiritual and educational work.

In the pedagogy of developed countries, the development and wide use of concepts such as "leisure pedagogy" (HP), "social-cultural animation", which reveal the spiritual-educational, educational essence of the issue of leisure, from the point of view of the pedagogy of spiritual-educational works is of great importance. Socio-cultural animation is intended not only to entertain the audience before every event, but also to help and enrich the meaning of each participant.

Social information is information that is prepared, transmitted, promoted by experts, aimed at providing information for the development of the country, reflecting specific knowledge, feelings, attitudes and ideas of voluntary mobilization. An example of this is the technology called the "Factory of Dreams", which was created in the 30s of the 20th century during the Great Depression . At that time, the government united the most mature intellectual forces of the nation and created images of beautiful life, human relations, and heroes of the times through Hollywood films. Hollywood was able to create a new modern image as an example in the social memory of the people.

Harmonization of recreational and social pedagogical views is a great contribution to the spiritual education of young people. This approach is also noteworthy as it aims to ensure the strategic tasks of cultural policy in Europe. We can see this strategic harmony in the example of the following recommendations aimed at increasing the educational effectiveness of European museums and libraries.

Them:

museums should not be limited to exhibiting exhibits, but should provide explanations for each exhibit;

Museum visitors should be allowed not only to see the exhibits, but also to hold them. And then the audience's impression will increase;

in museums, conditions should be created for visitors to rest, relax and enjoy themselves.

Social and educational orientation should be an important function of local libraries. It is revealed in the form of clear instructions that they should work at convenient times for the population.

"A natural salon" and "Philosophical salon" which are widely used in European countries . These educational salons were initially opened in France by Dorothea and Marie-Pierre, two friends and students who were literary geniuses. Their specialties are not literary studies, they are united by love for literature. They come to " A natural salon" to escape from everyday life and talk about love, happiness, loyalty, betrayal, chaos. Every Friday, 20 salon fans gather on the banks of the Seine. They are thirty years old on average. They sit on chairs and discuss the interpretation of the problems of love and loneliness in Marcel Proust's work from morning till night. They prepare for every meeting and bring many books with them. The margins of the book will be full of their writings.

A similar scene can be seen in Marc Sothe's "philosophical salon". More than 40 "salons " gather once a week to discuss "Where is humanity going?", "Is humanity developing?" they discuss issues such as In addition, in Paris , educational clubs and associations such as " Philosophy Cafe", " A Natural Salon", "Poetry Circle", "Dinner of History Fans" can be found in the cities of Dijon, Nice, and Strasbourg.

The main principles of spiritual and educational work in our country are scientificity, systematicity, historicity, accuracy and speed, regularity, reliance on real life examples, harmony of educational work, consistency of the propaganda

process, spiritual-spiritual Relying on the positive results and achievements achieved in the field work can serve as important methodological links of the integration of national and foreign experience.

Based on this comparative approach, research was conducted on the enrichment of the technologies of the practice of spiritual and educational work in our country. As a result of them, on the one hand, on the one hand, dozens of methods, forms, and tools were identified, which are present in the national technological base, but are not used due to the lack of scientific study, classification, and methodological support. They were classified, described, and provided with scientific recommendations on their introduction to the directions of spiritual and educational work. As a result of the conducted researches, a socio-pedagogical assortment of methods, forms, tools proposed for wide use in the activity of the Republican Spirituality and Enlightenment Center system was developed.

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